

TRAFFIC CONGESTION PREDICTION IN SATELLITE BROADBAND COMMUNICATIONS

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Abstract

Operating a satellite network involves multiple disciplines and layers that may congest at some moments. In particular, sudden traffic demands due to massive events may produce congestion at traffic level, causing outage. This can be solved by performing smart and optimized resource management. However, managing resources in a satellite payload is not fast as desired and may take some minutes or hours to finalize a particular resource allocation. Therefore, having a forecast of traffic congestion is a necessary tool to anticipate and react before the congestion occurs. In this paper we propose a novel approach of traffic congestion prediction by using Deep Learning techniques to produce a forecast. Aimed by real data provided by a European satellite operator, we show that it is possible perform a forecast of traffic congestion in the following two hours to manage the resources more efficiently to reduce the outage under heavily congested moments.

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1 Introduction

Satellite resources are limited and finite. Managing them efficiently is a paramount task that must be monitored 24/7 to guarantee an adequate quality of experience. Determining the number of channels, the power budget, the bit rate, the modulation and coding scheme (MODCOD), etc. are parameters that are optimized at every day [1][3][3]. Predicting the demand of users' needs is essential for efficient planning within satellite operators and can supply the optimal solution to these questions. Even when a smaller number of forecasts are needed, there may be no one sufficiently trained in the use of predictive models. In these circumstances, an automatic forecasting algorithm can be a valuable tool.

The allocation of resources for each beam is necessary to optimize the overall network efficiency. In a flexible multibeam system, the satellite generates a variable beam pattern composed by B beams to cover the whole desired area. In order to optimize the resources, the capacity $C_b(\mathbf{t})$ of each beam b at each time instant \mathbf{t} must be adjusted to the incoming throughput $R_b(\mathbf{t})$. Therefore, the objective function is the minimization of the difference between the adjusted capacity compared to the required throughput:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{R_b(\mathbf{t})} \sum_b \|C_b(\mathbf{t}) - R_b(\mathbf{t})\|^2 \\ \text{s. t.} \quad R_b(\mathbf{t}) \leq C_b(\mathbf{t}) \\ C_b(\mathbf{t}) \in \mathcal{R} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{R} is the total finite and discrete set of available throughputs. In general, $C_b(\mathbf{t})$ depends on the assigned power to the b th beam and the set of available throughputs is a set of achievable rates depending on the accepted MODCOD defined in the used standard.

In (1), assuming that a carrier serves a single user, the capacity and

$$C_b(\mathbf{t}) = \sum_c^c W_c \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_c}{\sigma_\omega^2} \right) \text{ [bps]} \quad (2)$$

where C is the total of carriers available in beam b , W_c is the assigned bandwidth the the c th carrier, P_c is the received power and σ_ω^2 is the total noise. Note that the receiver power contains gains and losses between the satellite and the terminal, and the total noise depends on the assigned bandwidth.

In general, this solution can be found via convex optimization methods. However, it has a strong dependence with the demanded traffic $R_b(\mathbf{t})$ and it becomes a problem if, for a particular time instant \mathbf{t} , there is not sufficient power to satisfy all demands. Therefore, it is necessary to know a priori or estimate the demanded traffic.

Estimating the demanded traffic allows to make a resource planning. If this planning cannot fulfil all the requirements, users will adjust their demands depending on the allocated throughput. At the same time, the allocated throughput depends on the adjusted capacity. These adjustments are performed progressively, as users' demands are modified gradually.

Forecasting the demands is the key process described in this paper. It takes the history of the demands depending on multiple temporal parameters and performs a short-term forecast.

At the same time, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a major topic nowadays that embraces multiple disciplines and provide joint solutions for many specializations. In particular, AI is being studied in communication systems to introduce new paradigms that were not solved in the past. For instance, AI is applied in

areas of satellite communications, such as in the PHY [4], interference management [5] or satellite operations [6], as well as in more sophisticated systems [7][8].

However, to our best knowledge, there is no approach on forecasting user demands in satellite networks. Despite forecast aimed with Deep Learning is applied in many areas [9][10][11][12], performing users' traffic demands in satellite networks is still unexplored.

2 Methodology

In this paper we aim at making a time prediction of the network congestion for a particular beam at link level. With a prediction, the satellite operator is able to anticipate to future outages and reallocate resources to reduce the network pressure in a particular moment.

We define the congestion metric as the ratio between the traffic consumption and capacity of the link:

$$G = \frac{T}{C} \quad (3)$$

where G is the congestion, T is the throughput and C is the link capacity, defined by the Shannon's capacity.

From a practical point of view, satellite operators do not monitor the time evolution of Shannon's capacity. Instead, they periodically poll the link to measure the maximum achievable throughput. In that case, it is preferable to define the congestion metric as:

$$G = \frac{T}{T^*} \quad (4)$$

where T^* is the maximum achievable throughput. T^* can be measured by using speed test tools periodically. Note that G is a ratio, which is dimensionless and it is comprised between 0 and 1.

Besides the congestion metric, we are also interested in the time evolution of the throughput, the maximum achievable throughput and the allocated symbol rate by the satellite operator. This last parameter is especially interesting in those transmissions that use the standard DVB-S2 since it defines the number of symbols per second that will be used in that link.

We consider 4 features for the proposed neural network that will be used for the prediction:

- Congestion.
- Throughput.
- Maximum Achievable Throughput.
- Symbol Rate.

These features will be used as the input of the proposed neural network. It is important that all the features must share the same granularity. Each consecutive sample in each feature represents the same temporal evolution.

To perform a prediction on the time evolution of the congestion, we combine several neural networks:

- Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) [13]: this network is focused on extracting hidden patterns amongst the input signals. Since we are using multiple features that might present some correlations, the use of a CNN will exploit the presence of such correlations.
- Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [14]: this network is focused on exploiting temporal correlations of each signal. In our case, we employ several LSTM with and without feedback.

By combining these neural networks, we are able to perform multiple predictions with flexible granularity based on the most recent history of each feature.

2.1 Pre-processing

Before taking the features to the whole neural network, each feature must be processed. This step is necessary and involves the following aspects:

- Normalize the data: each feature might have different statistics, can be biased or different power. Thus, it is necessary to normalized by subtracting the bias and dividing by the standard deviation:

$$F'_i = \frac{F_i - \mu_i}{\sigma_i} \quad (5)$$

where F'_i is the normalized feature, F_i is the i -th feature, μ_i is the bias of the i -th feature and σ_i is the standard deviation of the i -th feature.

- Arrange the data: usually the data of each feature has different dimensions. All data must have the same data format.
- Fill the gaps: it is not infrequent that at some instant, data is missing for a feature. In these cases, the data must be filled either with zeros, ones, repeating the last value, etc. This task must be done for each feature individually.
- Remove spurious or outliers: some values may be wrong as an anomaly or fault in the sensor. Prior to processing, the data has to be analysed by human inspection.

2.2 Processing

Before starting the processing, we define the relevant parameters that will be used by the neural network, the hyperparameters:

- History size (H): this is the size, in samples, of the historical data that will be used to update the prediction.

- Granularity (g): the temporal space between consecutive samples.
- Prediction size (P): the number of consecutive samples to be predicted.
- Number of neurons/cells: the number of neurons of the CNN and the number of cells of LSTM.
- Loss metric: this is the metric used to obtain the results of the losses. It can be the Mean Square Error (MSE), the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), the Cosine Proximity (CP), etc.

In our case, the approach is based on slicing temporal window of size $H + P$ samples. The temporal span is, thus, $(H + P)g$.

For the training phase, we iterate over the whole set of features by moving the slicing window and make the prediction for the next P samples. Later, the prediction is compared with the true samples of the future by applying the chosen loss metric. Then, the states of the neural network are adjusted to produce a prediction with less losses. This iterative process is stopped when the reduction of the losses is irrelevant and when the slicing window arrives to the end of the training set.

When the training is finished, the internal state of the neural network is prepared to receive actual samples during the inference phase.

2.3 Inference stage

Once the neural network is trained, we are able to perform predictions based on the incoming date. The network learnt the hidden patterns and is able to track the trend in the next hours. Despite it is not track fast variations and peaky traffic, it is able to anticipate the congestion by inferencing the traffic prediction.

For simplicity, we employed the same parameters (H , g and P) to construct the slicing window, though other values may be used. In our case, we assume the data is continuously flowing from the source (i.e., the traffic volume). However, in some restrictive scenarios, it may not be possible to sustain this inference in a continuous mode.

In this scenario, the network has to be called asynchronously by providing a date and time in order to guarantee the data is correctly processed. Additionally, it is important to maintain a fix value for the granularity to avoid misvalues on the gradient computations.

The procedure to obtain a prediction is similar to the training stage: the network is input with a vector corresponding to the traffic volume in each time mark, equally spaced with a granularity of g . The output of the network is a vector of predictions in ascending order, starting from the next g time mark, $2g$, $3g$, etc.

An optimal configuration is obtained when $H = P$, i.e., the size of the history window equals to the prediction window.

For instance, to produce a prediction of the traffic congestion within the next two hours, we need a historical data of the traffic of the past two hours.

2.4 Architecture

In the literature, there are many types of deep learning networks, able to perform multiple operations and solve different problems. In our case, we focus on two: CNN and LSTM.

On one hand, a CNN is a type of neural network that is based on the structure and work of the first layers of vision of the brain. A CNN is made up of two main parts: one that oversees extracting information from the data and another that is in charge of classifying it.

In the first part of this network, feature extraction, we extract the information from the data. We perform a method called convolution. It extracts the main qualities of the data by obtaining repetitive hidden patterns.

The convolution process consists of gradually reducing the dimensions of the data in such a way that we keep the most relevant, which gives us more information to be able to classify it correctly. This first phase holds the largest number of layers in the network.

In the second part, the classification task is performed. This last phase holds only two layers of neurons: the first receives the information that comes from the feature extraction and passes it to the output layer that performs a decision.

Hence, in general, convolutional models are composed by several dense layers, but they also contain convolutional layers. The convolutional layer performs the mathematical convolution of the inputs in two directions (features and time). This introduces an extra degree of exploitation since it is able to extract joint hidden patterns amongst features and time.

On the other hand, LSTM is an artificial recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture used in the field of Deep Learning. Unlike standard feedback neural networks, LSTM has feedback connections. It can not only process individual data points (i.e., images), but also entire data streams (such as voice or video inputs). Furthermore, LSTM models can store information for a period. That is, they have memory capacity.

This feature is extremely useful when it comes to time series or sequential data, as in traffic prediction scenarios. When we use an LSTM model, we are able to decide what information will be stored and what will be discarded. This is implemented by using a mathematical concept named *doors*.

LSTMs can add and removing information from the state of the cell, through structures called gates. These doors are a way to pass information when necessary. They are composed of a sigmoid neural network layer (σ) together with a point with a multiplication operation.

LSTM networks manage to keep contextual information of inputs by integrating a loop that allows information to flow

from one step to the next. In contrast to Convolution Neural Networks (CNN), LSTM networks do not use neurons as processing units, but elementary cells

In a LSTM, there are three gates to control the flow of information: the input gate, the output gate and the forget gate. The first balances the amount of information that goes into the cell; the second, the amount of information that goes out from the cell; the third, the amount of information that remains inside the cell. Usually, the hyperbolic tangent function, tanh, is employed to update the cell and hidden states. The sigmoid function is used for the activation of the three gates.

3 Results

In our results, we employed a very large dataset, composed by the following features:

- Historical traffic volume within a full month, with a granularity of 5 minutes ($g = 5$).
- Maximum achievable throughput, measured in bits per second (bps).
- Symbol rate, in symbols per second. This is a fixed parameter of the transmission, used to compute the forward link throughput.
- The historical congestion, by applying (4).

In summary, the inputs are four vectors (with millions of samples), where each sample corresponds to the time mark of 5 minutes.

Figure 1 depicts the snapshots of the data sets used in our results.

Figure 1. Snapshots of the data sets for symbol rate, traffic demand (labelled as *mbps*) and maximum achievable capacity (labelled as *fwc_volume*) for the beam 160.

In order to balance the memory and capacity of reaction, we designed the slicing window with $H = P = 12$, yielding a

history window of 2 hours for predictions of every 5 minutes in the next 2 hours.

To perform the training and inference, we utilize a dedicated workstation, equipped with two RTX 3090, with more than 20 000 GPU cores to parallelize the computations and with more than 40 GB of integrated memory. The deep learning network is constructed on top of the TensorFlow framework.

3.1 Prediction results

First, we divide the whole dataset in three parts, for the training, test and validation with a proportion of 70%, 20% and 10%, respectively. This data is used to train our deep learning network. Once finished, we are able to use the network to perform predictions online based on current traffic.

Figure 2 depicts the incoming traffic (blue upper curve) and the predicted (orange lines). Green lines depict the expected traffic, which matches with the incoming traffic. Note that, despite orange and green curves are superposed, orange curve is generated before the green curve, since it is a prediction. This prediction is completely blind and within two hours in the future. As we mentioned, the algorithm is unable to predict spurious traffic and traffic outliers. In contrast, it is effectively able to predict the trends and, the most important, is able to anticipate to trends variations. For instance, it is able to predict a significant traffic increase that may lead into a congestion in two hours future.

Figure 2. Prediction and expected traffic volume.

With these results, the satellite operator is able to anticipate the satellite resources to mitigate the potential congestion and guarantee the quality of service and thus, it aims at reducing the global outage of satellite services caused by traffic congestion.

Figure 3 depicts a detailed view of the prediction in seven-time frames. Each subplot corresponds to a different non-consecutive time interval. As aforementioned, the prediction tracks the trend of the incoming traffic and is able to predict whether the traffic will increase or not.

Figure 3. Detailed prediction and expected traffic volume.

3.2 Performance evaluation

In order to analyse the performance of the proposed algorithm we employ three metrics: the Mean Square Error (MSE), the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Cosine Proximity (CP).

- Mean Squared Error (MSE): this metric is employed to calculate the loss of learning. Lower loss implies more reliability.
- Mean Absolute Error (MAE): this metric is employed to analyse the overall error produced by the algorithm.
- Cosine Proximity (CP): this metric is used to analyse the error deviation of the results.

After the training stage, all these metrics for each iteration are stored and visualized in the TensorBoard tool. To decide on the success of the training, we use the following criteria:

1. Training MSE and MAE shall converge.
2. Training MSE and MAE shall decrease.
3. Training and validation shall not diverge.

If training and validation curves diverge, it may imply that overfitting is occurring. In this case, a recommendation is to reduce the neural network complexity by reducing the neurons or the number of layers to decrease the specialization.

Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6 depict the performance of the proposed algorithm for the training and validation steps at each iteration. These plots are useful to observe the convergence of the performance. As we expected, the performance is stabilized with a value. Once it detects the performance is stabilized, it stops the algorithm to avoid unnecessary computation and energy consumption. In our case, it is achieved at the 14th iteration. As expected, all metrics converge and stabilize to a threshold after a period of iterations.

Figure 4. MSE of training (blue) and validation (red).

Figure 5. MAE of training (blue) and validation (red).

Figure 6. CP of training (blue) and validation (red).

3.3 Multi beam

One of the advantages of the proposed networks is the independency from other beams. Usually, the beams of a satellite are used to cover different areas of a region on the globe with small overlap. Therefore, each beam may have its own traffic patterns depending on the population of this area, its habits or customs. Therefore, it is recommended to run the proposed architecture in parallel for each beam.

Comparing the metrics MSE, MAE and CP, all produce distinct values depending on the beam. In the following figures, we utilized the data traffic of several beams (regions)

provided by a European satellite operator. Furthermore, the differences between beams are not proportional. For instance, CP may increase and MSE may decrease compared with another beam. For this reason, having multiple metrics is especially useful.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 depict the results of MSE, MAE and CP metrics for multiple beams. As aforementioned, there is no correlation between pair of beams and thus, it is recommended to run the algorithm in parallel for each beam.

Figure 7. MSE, MAE and CP metrics comparison for different beams for the validation data set.

Figure 8. MSE, MAE and CP metrics comparison for different beams for the test data set.

In order to compare the beams, we compute the correlation matrix of the data traffic and maximum achievable rate. This matrix computes the cross-correlation between two pairs of signals and assigns a colour depending on the value. For simplicity, the correlations are normalized to produce a result between 0 and 1.

Figure 9 and Figure 10 depict the correlation matrix for multiple beams for data traffic and maximum achievable rate. From Figure 9 we can observe a high correlation between

beams 1147 and 148. The next cluster is composed by beams 155 – 160. All these beams have strong cross-correlation, meaning that the traffic is significantly similar.

Under these special cases, we can infer the results from one beam to another. For instance, we can run the algorithm with the aggregated data of both beams to produce a single prediction, valid for both. Note that, however, the correlation matrix detects a correlation between two signals but does not describe the shift of this correlation, meaning that both traffics are correlated but shifted in time.

Figure 10 depicts cross-correlation of the maximum achievable rate for pairs of beams. As we expect, since it is a magnitude that depends on the physical aspects of the link, we cannot appreciate significant correlations compared with Figure 9.

Figure 9. Correlation matrix of traffic.

Figure 10. Correlation matrix of maximum achievable rate.

4 Conclusions

In this paper we present a novel approach based on deep learning techniques to perform traffic congestion predictions based on current and historical traffic. The result is a set of predictions, equally time spaced, within a time frame in the future. It allows the satellite operators to observe traffic trends variations and anticipate to unexpected traffic increases in order to accommodate the satellite resources to satisfy the upcoming demands and mitigate the potential outage. The results unveiled that the proposed architecture is able to track the traffic trends and anticipate to unexpected traffic increases.

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